

Studies on acoustical properties of poly(4,4'-diphenylphthalidediphenyl-4,4'-disulfonate) at 30°

D. R. Godhani^a and P. H. Parsania^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005, India

E-mail : phparsania@yahoo.com Fax : 91-0281-578512

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Several acoustical parameters of poly(4,4'-diphenylphthalidediphenyl-4,4'-disulfonate)-1,2-dichloroethane, THF and DMF solutions (0.5–4.0%) at 30° have been determined from density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity (2 MHz) data to understand solvophilicity and solvophobicity of the polymer under investigation. Powerful solvent-polymer interaction and hence solvophilicity is supported by linear increase of U , Z , R , b , π , $(\alpha/f^2)_{Cl}$ and τ and linear decrease of K_s , r and V_f with C . Polymer has structure-forming tendency in all the three solvent systems. DMF and THF have more solvating tendency than 1, 2-dichloroethane.

Ultrasonic velocity and related parameters are very important in characterization of polymers : the structure of polymers and molecular interactions occurring in the solutions^{1–5}. To our knowledge no work has been reported on acoustical properties of polysulfonates of phenolphthalein solutions. With a view of technological demand of ultrasonic studies of polymeric solutions, the present communication reports the studies on acoustical properties of poly(4,4'-diphenyl-phthalidediphenyl-4,4'-disulfonate) (PHDP) solutions at 30°.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data on ρ , η and U of pure solvents and PHDP solutions at 30° are reported in Table 1. It is found graphically that ρ , η and U increased linearly with concentration (C) and the observed trend in ρ is DCE > DMF > THF; η is DMF > DCE > THF and U is DMF > THF > DCE. With a view to understand solvophilicity and solvophobicity of PHDP in solutions, several acoustical parameters were determined, by using the above data, according to standard equations⁶ and are correlated with C . The least-square equations along with the correlation coefficients (γ) are reported in Table 2. From Table 2, it is evident that good to excellent correlation is observed be-

Table 1. The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data of PHDP solutions at 30°

Concn. %	THF	DCE		DMF
		$10^{-3} \rho, \text{kg m}^{-3}$		
0.0	0.8837	1.2449	1.2449	0.9443
0.5	0.8859	1.2461	1.2461	0.9466
1.0	0.8886	1.2466	1.2466	0.9475
1.5	0.8904	1.2476	1.2476	0.9493
2.0	0.8944	1.2489	1.2489	0.9509
3.0	0.8974	1.2493	1.2493	0.9542
4.0	0.8992	1.2499	1.2499	0.9572
		$10^3 \eta, \text{PaS}$		
0.0	0.4801	0.7422	0.7422	0.7581
0.5	0.5305	0.8322	0.8322	0.8844
1.0	0.5922	0.9262	0.9262	1.0406
1.5	0.6625	1.0402	1.0402	1.2051
2.0	0.7914	1.1885	1.1885	1.3871
3.0	1.0021	1.5751	1.5751	1.9043
4.0	1.1742	2.0450	2.0450	2.5513
		$U, \text{m s}^{-1}$		
0.0	1232.4	1150.2	1150.2	1440.0
0.5	1244.6	1152.2	1152.2	1442.6
1.0	1246.8	1155.6	1155.6	1445.2
1.5	1250.0	1160.8	1160.8	1446.4
2.0	1254.8	1172.0	1172.0	1452.0
3.0	1259.0	1176.8	1176.8	1455.2
4.0	1263.0	1184.2	1184.2	1457.4

Table 2. The least-square equations and correlation coefficients (ϕ) for PHDP solutions at 30°

Parameter	Correlation equation (Correlation coefficient)		
	THF	DCE	DMF
$\rho \times 10^{-3}$, kg m ⁻³	$\rho = 0.8849$ + 0.0039C (0.9766)	$\rho = 1.2458$ + 0.0011C (0.9530)	$\rho = 0.9447$ + 0.0031C (0.9985)
$\eta \times 10^3$, PaS	$\eta = 0.4083$ + 0.1919C (0.9965)	$\eta = 0.5689$ + 0.3495C (0.9882)	$\eta = 0.5455$ + 0.4750C (0.9895)
U , m s ⁻¹	$U = 1242.1$ + 5.4471C (0.9901)	$U = 1147.9$ + 9.5176C (0.9784)	$U = 1441.5$ + 4.3176C (0.9769)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$, kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	$Z = 1.0990$ + 0.0098C (0.9854)	$Z = 1.4302$ + 0.0131C (0.9761)	$Z = 1.3618$ + 0.0086C (0.9946)
$K_s \times 10^{10}$, Pa ⁻¹	$K_s = 7.3218$ - 0.0934C (0.9864)	$K_s = 6.0869$ - 0.1008C (0.9761)	$K_s = 5.0921$ - 0.0455C (0.9894)
$R \times 10^4$, m ^{10/3} s ^{-1/3} mol ⁻¹	$R = 8.7631$ + 0.6719C (0.9999)	$R = 8.3193$ + 0.3523C (1.0000)	$R = 8.7766$ + 0.5996C (0.9989)
$b \times 10^5$, m ³	$b = 6.8951$ + 0.4904C (0.9949)	$b = 6.7045$ + 0.2416C (0.9867)	$b = 6.4396$ + 0.4689C (0.9973)
r	$r = 0.3973$ - 0.0054C (0.9904)	$r = 0.4853$ - 0.0087C (0.9794)	$r = 0.1881$ - 0.0048C (0.9758)
$(\alpha/\beta^2)_{Cl} \times 10^{14}$ s ² m ⁻¹	$(\alpha/\beta^2)_{Cl} =$ 1.671 + 0.245C (0.921)	$(\alpha/\beta^2)_{Cl} =$ 2.408 + 0.370C (0.878)	$(\alpha/\beta^2)_{Cl} =$ 2.090 + 0.369C (0.886)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$, s	$\tau = 4.0687$ + 1.7169C (0.9966)	$\tau = 4.7923$ + 2.5460C (0.9878)	$\tau = 3.8103$ + 3.061C (0.9895)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$, Pa	$\pi = 3.9862$ + 0.1683C (0.9627)	$\pi = 4.3896$ + 0.4567C (0.9940)	$\pi = 4.7828$ + 0.4468C (0.9970)
$V_f \times 10^8$, m ³	$V_f = 27.657$ - 4.3458C (0.9783)	$V_f = 19.978$ - 3.6281C (0.9941)	$V_f = 16.077$ - 3.0823C (0.9853)

tween specified parameters and C except the solvation number (S_n) (Fig. 1), apparent molar volume (ϕV_2) (Fig. 2) and apparent molar compressibility (ϕK_s) (Fig. 3) which varied nonlinearly with C .

The linear increase of ultrasonic velocity (U), specific acoustical impedance (Z), Rao's molar sound function (R), Van der Waals constant (b), classical absorption coefficient $(\alpha/\beta^2)_{Cl}$, viscous relaxation time (τ), internal pressure (π), linear decrease in isentropic compressibility (K_s), relaxation

Fig. 1. The plots of solvation number vs C at 30°.

strength (r) and free volume (V_f) with C suggested powerful polymer-solvent interactions¹⁻⁷. The polymeric chains are more compressible and it is supported³ by decrease in K_s with C . Moreover, the solvophilicity of PHDP is confirmed from linear increase of π and decrease of V_f with C and the positive values of S_n (Fig. 1). The intermolecular forces (Van der Waals, H-bonding, dipolar and London forces) between polymer and solvent molecules result in the formation of aggregates of solvent molecules around polymer molecules^{2,3} and hence modification of the polymer structure due to increase in cohesive forces.

The solvophilicity also causes change in the apparent molar volume as well as apparent molecular weight. The nonlinear increase of ϕV_2 (Fig. 2) and ϕK_s (Fig. 3) with C

Fig. 2. The plots of apparent molar volume vs C at 30°.

Fig. 3. The plots of apparent molar compressibility vs C at 30°.

are in support of the existence of strong molecular interactions. The solvophilicity or solvophobicity can be judged on the basis of type of molecular interactions. The lone-pairs of electrons of solvent(s) (THF, DMF) and PHDP (sulfonate and phthalide oxygen) and chlorine (DCE) are electronegative groups while hydrogen, methyl (DMF) and phenyl rings are electropositive groups. The solvophilicity is favored due to dipole-dipole interaction of opposite type while solvophobicity is favored by dipole-dipole interaction of the same type. It is more likely that hydrogen and methyl groups of DMF interact strongly with sulfonate and phthalide oxygen of PHDP to form H-bond and it is less probable with lone-pairs of electrons of carbonyl and amide oxygen of DMF with phenyl rings due to steric hindrance. Similarly, THF oxygen and chlorine of DCE favor H-bond formation with phenyl rings but interaction with sulfonate and phthalide oxygen disfavors the structure formation. In present case, a powerful structure-forming tendency is observed in DMF system. The structure-forming tendency is observed with *C* in all the three solvent systems studied. The dipole-dipole interaction of opposite type favors structure-forming tendency while opposite type favors structure-breaking tendency. Thus, the net effect would be dependent on the type of the interactions that exists in the solutions. On the basis of experimental findings, it is concluded that a powerful solvophilicity is observed in the solvent systems investigated. DMF has more solvophilicity towards PHDP. Moreover, solvophilicity is found to increase with concentration.

Experimental

Poly(4,4'-diphenylphthalidediphenyl-4,4'-disulfonate) (PHDP) was synthesized⁸ and purified from 1,2-dichloro-

ethane-methanol system prior to use. 1,2-Dichloroethane (DCE), tetrahydrofuran and *N,N*-dimethylformamide were purified by reported methods⁹. The ultrasonic velocity (*U*) (2 MHz, Mittal Enterprises), viscosity (η) and density (ρ) measurements on pure solvents DCE, THF and DMF, and polymer solutions (0.5 to 4.0%) were carried out at 30±0.1°. The precision and accuracy of η , *U* and ρ measurements were ±0.2%, ±0.1% and ±0.0001 g cm⁻³, respectively.

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